

Binding interaction of photoactive drug Merocyanine 540 with fiber like protein spectrin : A spectroscopic approach[†]

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Abstract : Merocyanine 540 (MC 540) belongs to the family of benzoxazolmerocyanine dyes with heterocyclic aromatic groups linked by a polymethine chain. Optical characteristics of such compounds are very sensitive to the changes in environmental factors, which make it a useful tool in biophysical research. We have studied the binding interaction of MC 540 with a fiber like network forming protein, spectrin, which was reported to interact with a large number of other proteins, e.g. actin, adducin, ankyrin and band 4.1, and also with a variety of hydrophobic ligands, tertiary amine local anesthetics and antitumor antibiotics chromomycin and mithramycin. Spectrin binds with MC 540 with a moderate affinity that has been studied using absorption and fluorescence spectroscopy. Thermodynamic basis of such a binding of MC 540 to erythroid spectrin is also understood from fluorescence quenching data. In addition to the evaluation of the binding affinities and associated thermodynamic parameters, the circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy also throws light on the structural basis of recognition and conformational changes of the membrane skeletal protein, spectrin bound with the drug MC 540. Theoretical docking studies help to predict probable binding site of MC 540 in spectrin.

Keywords : Erythroid spectrin, fluorescence, time-resolved fluorescence, merocyanine, binding constant.

Introduction

Merocyanine 540 (MC 540) belongs to the family of benzoxazolmerocyanine dyes with heterocyclic aromatic groups linked by a polymethine chain (Fig. 1a). Optical characteristics of such compounds are very sensitive to the changes in environmental factors, such as polarity, viscosity, and temperature¹, which makes it a useful tool in biophysical research. MC 540 was used in a variety of investigations including monitoring of transmembrane potential in biological samples⁶⁻⁹. Moreover, preferential uptake of MC 540 by certain neoplastic cells and viruses and phototoxicity of this dye were reported earlier⁶. As a result, application of MC 540 in photo chemotherapeutic treatment of leukemia and certain virus-infected cells was suggested⁹.

Spectrin is the major constituent protein of the erythrocyte cytoskeleton that forms a filamentous network on

Fig. 1a. Molecular structure of Merocyanine 540.

the cytoplasmic face of the membrane (Fig. 1b). Spectrin is composed of two largest known, evolutionarily related polypeptide chains, α -subunit (280 kDa) and β -subunit (246 kDa), both of which are non-covalently associated in an antiparallel 'side-to-side' manner to form a two-stranded worm-like heterodimer¹¹. It is noteworthy that the 106 amino acid long repeat units in spectrin have

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

Fig. 1b. Tetrameric structure of spectrin.

tryptophans strongly conserved at the 45th residue and partially conserved at the 11th residue¹¹⁻¹⁵. The tryptophans in these positions represent more than 60% of the total tryptophans in the spectrin dimer. Due to the planar network spectrin interacts with a large number of proteins such as actin, adducin, ankyrin and protein 4.1. In addition to those proteins spectrin binds to a variety of hydrophobic ligands, tertiary amine local anaesthetics and antitumor antibiotics chromomycin and mithramycin¹⁶⁻²¹. It also contains a large number of binding sites for fatty acids and its derivatives²¹, phospholipids²², ATP along the length of the large worm-like protein molecule.

In the present work we show a moderate affinity binding between spectrin and MC 540 using fluorescence spectroscopy. We also attempt to understand the thermodynamic basis of such a binding of MC 540 to erythroid spectrin. In addition to the evaluation of the binding affinities and associated thermodynamic parameters, we have employed circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy to throw light on the structural basis of recognition and conformational changes of the membrane skeletal protein spectrin associated with this drug binding.

2. Materials and methods

Merocyanine 540, Tris, phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF), dithiothreitol (DTT), and EDTA have been purchased from Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA). Deionised water, twice distilled on quartz, has been used for preparing solutions and buffers. The CD spectra have been recorded in a Jasco 720 spectropolarimeter. CD spectra in the range 200–250 nm have been recorded in a cylindrical cuvette of 1 mm path length. All spectra are the average of six runs. Each spectrum has been subtracted from the buffer baseline and smoothed within the permissible limits using the in-built software of the instrument. Dimeric spectrin has been purified from white erythro-

cyte ghosts prepared by hypotonic lysis in 5 mM phosphate, 1 mM EDTA containing 20 g/ml PMSF at pH 8.0 following published protocols^{16,17}. Spectrin extraction has been done by resuspending the erythrocyte ghosts in 20 vol. of spectrin removal buffer (0.2 mM sodium phosphate, 0.1 mM EDTA, 0.2 mM DTT, 20 g/ml PMSF, pH 8.0), and incubating at 37°C for 30 min. The crude spectrin has been purified after concentrate by 30% ammonium sulfate precipitation elaborated earlier²³. Spectrin has been stored in the buffer containing 5 mM phosphate, 20 mM KCl, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8.0 containing 0.2 mM DTT and dialyzed extensively against the buffer containing 20 mM Tris-HCl, 50 mM NaCl, pH 7.4 to remove DTT before all fluorescence experiments. Spectrin concentrations have been determined spectrophotometrically from an absorbance of 10.7 at 280 nm for 1% spectrin solution²⁴.

2.1. Absorption measurements

The absorption spectra have been recorded on a Jasco V-650 absorption spectrophotometer over a wavelength range from 250 to 500 nm. A 1 cm path length cuvette was used. In order to show the adduct formation between spectrin and MC 540, absorption spectroscopy has been used. In this method, first 2 mL of 1×10^{-6} M MC 540 was placed in a sample chamber along with the same volume of buffer in the reference cell and the absorption spectrum has been recorded. The MC 540 absorbance has been titrated with the sequential addition of a spectrin to the sample and reference cuvette both calculated over the concentration range from 0 to 0.7×10^{-6} M.

2.2. Fluorescence measurements

Steady-state fluorescence measurements between 310 to 500 nm, with an excitation wavelength of 295 nm, have been performed in a Fluoromax-400 spectrophotometer. The cuvette path length is 1 cm. The excitation and emission band passes have been fixed at 5 nm and 5 nm respectively.

2.3. Stern-Volmer plot for fluorescence quenching

The quenching of fluorescence was analyzed using the Stern-Volmer equation²⁵ :

$$\frac{F_0}{F} = 1 + K_{SV}[Q] \quad (1)$$

where F_0 and F are the relative fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively, K_{SV} is the Stern-Volmer constant and $[Q]$ is the concentration of the quencher.

$$K_{SV} = k_q \tau_0 \quad (2)$$

where k_q is the bimolecular quenching rate constant and τ_0 is the average lifetime of spectrin in the absence of MC 540. The k_q comes from the given equation²⁵

$$k_q = 4\pi a N_A \times 10^{-3} \quad (3)$$

where D is the sum of diffusion coefficients of fluorophore and quencher, a is the sum of molecular radii and N_A is the Avogadro's number.

2.4. Measurements of lifetime by time-correlated-single-photon counting device

Fluorescence lifetimes have been measured using a time-correlated-single-photon counting (TCSPC) spectrophotometer (Horiba Jobin Yovin) with FWHM ~ 790 ps, repetition rate 1 MHz. The excitation and emission wavelengths have been chosen to be 295 nm and 340 nm respectively.

2.5. Estimation of binding constant

The binding parameters i.e. binding affinity constant for the interaction between spectrin and MC 540 have been estimated from the quenching of protein fluorescence at maximum emission (340 nm) with excitation at 295 nm, on subsequent addition of MC 540. The quenching data have been analyzed to determine the binding affinity constant (K_a) following the relation below which could be applicable for more than one binding site also^{26,27}.

$$\frac{1}{\Delta F} = \frac{1}{\Delta F_{\max}} + \frac{1}{\Delta F_{\max} \cdot K_a} \cdot \frac{1}{L} \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta F = F_0 - F$, F_0 and F denotes the protein fluorescence in the absence and presence of the ligand (L), respectively. ΔF_{\max} represents the maximum quenched fluorescence intensity obtained from the intercept of the linear plot of $1/\Delta F$ against $1/L$. The ΔF_{\max} has been determined from the intercept and the slope gives the value of the binding affinity constant (K_a).

2.6. Analysis of thermodynamic parameters

The thermodynamic characteristics for MC 540 binding with spectrin have been determined from the van't Hoff equation :

$$\ln K_a = - \frac{\Delta H^\circ}{RT} + \frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R} \quad (5)$$

where, K_a is the binding affinity constant at corresponding temperature T , and R is the gas constant. The equation gives the standard enthalpy change (ΔH°) and standard entropy change (ΔS°) on binding. The free energy change (ΔG°) has been estimated from the following relationship :

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (6)$$

2.7. Measurements of circular dichroism (CD)

The Far-UV CD spectra have been measured on a Jasco-720. The CD spectra of spectrin have been recorded in the absence and presence of MC540 using a 1 mm path length cuvette within the wavelength range of 190–250 nm. The CD results have been analyzed in terms of mean residue ellipticity (MRE) in $\text{deg cm}^2 \text{dmol}^{-1}$ according to the following equation²⁸ :

$$[\theta_\lambda] = \frac{\mu\theta}{10LC} \quad (7)$$

where C is the concentration of spectrin in g/ml, θ is observed rotation in degree, L is the path length in cm and μ is the mean residual molecular weight of protein. Quantitative assessment of the percentage of α -helix in spectrin in the presence and absence of MC 540 can be estimated by the relation of Chen *et al.*²¹ :

$$\% \text{ of } \alpha - \text{ helix} = \frac{[\theta]_{222} + 2340}{-30300} \quad (8)$$

$$\% \text{ of } \alpha - \text{ helix} = \frac{[\theta]_{208} + 4000}{33000 - 400} \quad (9)$$

2.8. Docking studies

Theoretical view of the HbA and MC 540 was established by using Docking study. The crystal structure of erythrocyte spectrin tetramerization domain complex (PDB entry 3LBX)²⁹ was downloaded from Protein Data Bank.

The Online Docking Server (<http://www.dockingserver.com>) was used to perform the docking calculations. The computational method used by the server is the following. The Dreiding force field has been used for energy minimization of ligand molecule using built-in Chemaxon tools in Docking Server. The Gasteiger partial charges have been added to the ligand atoms. Non-polar H atoms have been merged and rotatable bonds have been defined. Essential H atoms, Kollman united atom type charges and solvation parameters have been added with the aid of AutoDock tools. Affinity (grid) maps of $64 \times 96 \times 68$ Å grid points and 1 Å spacing have been generated using the Autogrid program. AutoDock parameter set and distance-dependent dielectric functions have been used in the calculation of the van der Waal's and the electrostatic terms respectively. Docking simulations have been performed using the Lamarckian genetic algorithm (LGA)³⁰⁻³² and the Slis and Wets local search method. Initial position, orientation and torsions of the ligand molecules have been set randomly. Each Docking experiment has been derived from 10 different runs that are set to terminate after a maximum of 250000 energy evaluations. The population size has been set to 150. During the search, a translational step of 0.2 Å, quaternion and torsion steps of 5 are applied. The output from AutoDock has been rendered with PyMOL³³. Here PyMOL has also been used to calculate the distances between nearest atoms which are interact with each other.

3. Results

3.1. Absorption measurements

Absorption spectra of free MC 540 in Tris buffer (20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4) show maxima (λ_{\max}) near ~ 502 nm and ~ 535 nm (Fig. 2), which correspond to dimer MC 540 ((MC 540)₂) and monomer MC 540 respectively that exist in equilibrium with each other. In an earlier report Sato and coworkers showed that the dissociation constant of monomer-dimer equilibrium in aqueous environment is 3.1×10^{-4} M at 25°C. However, at the concentration of MC 540 well below 10^{-5} M, both dimer and monomer co-exist. When spectrin is added in MC 540 solution the absorbance of MC 540 have been increases gradually with formation of one isosbestic point at 557 nm. That means in this present system ground state complex has been forms.

3.2. Fluorescence measurements

In the steady state fluorescence experiment spectrin

behaves as a fluorophore after photoexcitation at 295 nm due to the intrinsic fluorescence of its Trp residues, and the drug MC 540 behaves as a quencher. Upon gradually increasing in the drug concentration from 4 μ M to 52 μ M in spectrin (0.1 μ M) the fluorescence maximum of Trp (λ_{\max}) at 340 nm is quenched (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Ground state complex formation between MC 540 (1 μ M) and spectrin with varying concentration from 0 to 0.7 μ M.

The Stern-Volmer plot (eq. [1]) for quenching of spectrin by MC 540 has been shown in Fig. 3 (inset). The plot displays a nonlinear downward bending towards the X-axis. One of the reasons behind that might be the formation of exciplex. The other reasons for nonlinearity

Fig. 3. Variation of fluorescence intensity of spectrin (0.1 μ M) as function of MC 540 concentration (4–52 μ M) and inset shows the downward bending of S-V plot.

are either that the interacting molecules are charged species or more than one Trp residue is present in the protein²⁵. The formation of ground state complex is best demonstrated by the absorption spectra of MC 540 with increasing concentration of spectrin that support the nonlinearity of the S-V plot. Fig. 2 shows the formation of isosbestic point at 577 nm which is a clear indication of the formation of ground state complex. Spectrin has more than one Trp which have different accessibility towards the interacting drug MC 540. For this differential accessibility of Trp mainly shows this type of downward bending of S-V plot.

With the increase in temperature K_{SV} increases which in turn indicates the presence of dynamic quenching (Fig. 4, Table 1). Therefore, in this present interacting system both static and dynamic types of quenching occur.

The TCSPC data show a change in lifetime of spectrin on the addition of MC 540. The average fluorescence lifetime of Trp in spectrin is 4.94 ns (τ_0) which decreases

Fig. 4. S-V plot of spectrin-MC 540 interaction at three different temperatures with spectrin (0.1 μ M) as function of MC 540 concentration (4–52 μ M).

to 4.85 ns (τ) in presence of MC 540 indicating that the nature of the quenching is dynamic. With the help of K_{SV} and fluorescence lifetime (τ_0) values, a k_q value was determined from eq. (2) which is $4.82 \times 10^{12} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (at 30°C). The upper limit of k_q as $10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is for the diffusion control phenomenon (eq. [3])²⁵. So the higher magnitude of k_q indicates the possibility of other processes involved in such interactions.

3.3. Determination of binding constant

The binding affinity constant (K_a) has been determined from the steady state fluorescence data, with variation of the MC 540 concentration. The K_a value has been found to increase with increasing in temperature, which indicates the presence of dynamic quenching. The binding constant at 30°C is 7.82×10^4 (Fig. 5 and Table 1).

3.4. Thermodynamic study

There are mainly four types of noncovalent interactions namely hydrogen bonds, van der Waal's forces, electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions can play a significant role in ligands binding to proteins. Study of thermodynamic parameters is essential to predict the mode of interaction. From the van't Hoff plot (Fig. 6 and eqs. (5) and (6)), the thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have been determined as shown in Table 1. Increase in entropy ($\Delta S^\circ = 172.19 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) suggests that hydrophobic interaction exists between spectrin and MC 540. Moreover, the positive value of the change in enthalpy ($\Delta H^\circ = 2.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) indicates that the binding is entropy driven and the negative change in free energy value ($\Delta G^\circ = -28.12 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ at 30°C) suggests the spontaneity of the interaction between particular drug and protein³⁴.

3.5. Circular dichroism study

The far-UV CD spectra of spectrin exhibit two characteristic negative bands at 222 and 208 nm which indicate the extent of helicity of protein. In case of the spectrin-MC 540 systems there is no such significant changes are

Table 1. Binding constants at three temperatures and thermodynamic parameters of MC 540 binding with spectrin

Temperature (K)	K_{SV} (M^{-1})	K_q ($\text{M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	K_a (M^{-1})	R	ΔH° (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS° ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	ΔG° (kJ mol^{-1})
293	2.36×10^4	4.82×10^{12}	4.94×10^4	0.99734			-26.43
303	2.41×10^4	4.92×10^{12}	7.82×10^4	0.99914	2.4	172.19	-28.12
313	2.62×10^4	5.35×10^{12}	9.05×10^4	0.99776			-29.87
323	2.86×10^4	5.82×10^{12}	1.30×10^5	0.98937			-31.59

Fig. 5. Binding isotherm fluorescence intensity at 340 nm versus ligand concentration for the interaction of spectrin (0.1 μM) with MC 540 in 20 mM Tris-HCl, 50 mM NaCl buffer, pH 7.4 at 25°C. The excitation wavelength is 295 nm. Inset shows the double reciprocal plot of $1/\Delta F$ against $1/L$ to evaluate the binding affinity constant K_a of spectrin with MC 540 in the 20 mM Tris buffer, pH 7.5 at 25°C.

Fig. 6. Van't Hoff plot for the interaction of spectrin (0.1 μM) with MC 540 in 20 mM Tris-HCl, 50 mM NaCl buffer, pH 7.4.

Fig. 7. The far-UV CD spectra (200–250 nm) of spectrin (1.5 μM) alone (solid line) and in the presence of 1 and 3 μM MC 540 (dotted line) in 20 mM Tris-HCl, 50 mM NaCl buffer, pH 7.4 at 25°C.

found. Due to long fiber like structure of spectrin, MC 540 is not able to change the secondary structure of spectrin significantly (Fig. 7).

3.6. Docking results

The spectrin tetramerization complex was crystallized very recently where α -spectrin repeats 0–1 (magenta) complexed with β -spectrin repeats 16–17 (green). The full structure of spectrin is not yet known for this reason. In the present docking study one of the segments of spectrin tetramer has been considered. The docking analyses suggest the probable binding site of MC 540 (blue) in the spectrin tetramer, preferably at the interface between α partial repeat 0 and β partial repeat 17.

4. Conclusion

The binding association between erythrocyte membrane protein spectrin and antileukemic drug MC 540 has been

Fig. 8. The cartoon representation of the drug MC 540 docked to that particular erythrocyte spectrin tetramerization domain complex (PDB entry 3LBX) model.

investigated by different spectroscopic methods. Absorption spectrum of MC 540 changes in presence of spectrin that indicates a ground state complex formation and the steady-state fluorescence quenching of spectrin in presence of MC 540. It helps to evaluate their binding association constant. The significant downward bending of S-V plot suggests differential accessibility of Trp toward MC 540 because spectrin has a large number of Trp. The increment in the slope of the S-V plots with increase in temperature suggests the occurrence of dynamic quenching between MC 540 and spectrin. It has also been verified from the time resolved fluorescence experiments which show shortening of lifetime of spectrin on addition of MC 540. Therefore both static and dynamic quenching occurs when spectrin interacts with MC 540 in ground and excited states respectively. The thermodynamic results show that the interaction is spontaneous and hydrophobic in nature. No such significant change in the CD spectrum of spectrin in the region from 200 to 250 nm in presence of MC 540 indicates that the association does not hamper the helical backbone structure of spectrin. Blind docking studies indicate that MC 540 may bind at the interface of α spectrin and β spectrin of tetramerization complex of erythrocyte spectrin. Since spectrin is a natural membrane protein, therefore its interaction affinity with clinically important antileukemic drug MC 540 has significant importance.

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